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Ultra-thin Attachable Bipolar plate for High-Performance VRFB

PRESENTER

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MECHANICAL DESIGN LAB. with
ADVANCED MATERIALS

< Global Electricity Production >

< Production instability >

*QC = Quick Charging System

Biweekly Meeting

1. Risk of Fire and Explosion in the Li-ion based ESS

Li-ion Battery

Non-Aqueous Electrolyte

ESS Accident in Korea (2017-2022)

Source : Ministry of Trade, Industry and Energy.

- Risk of ignition and explosion.
- Relatively short lifetime.
- Power and capacity cannot be controlled independently.

July 2021 - 13-Ton Tesla Megapack Caught Fire

1. Vanadium Redox Flow Batteries (VRFBs)

Safety of ESS	Lithium-ion	<u>VRFB</u>	Flooded Cell	Sodium Sulfur
Over-voltage	X	O	X	X
Arc-Flash	X	O	X	X
Fire	X	O	X	X

- No risk of explosion and ignition / High durability of over 20 years.
- High design flexibility in power and capacity.
- Low energy efficiency and density of VRFB.

1. Vanadium Redox Flow Batteries (VRFBs)

Principle and Schematic of VRFB

Periodic Table of the Elements

23 V Vanadium 50.942

$V^{2+} \rightarrow V^{3+} \rightarrow V^{4+} \rightarrow V^{5+}$

Electrode

Porous media, Reactive area

- **Functional requirements of the electrode**
 - Large reactive area and reactivity
 - Excellent chemical durability
 - Low electrical resistance

1. Vanadium Redox Flow Batteries (VRFBs)

Half Cell of VRFB

- High electrical conductivity
- Low electrolyte permeability
- High rigidity (stiffness)

Graphite sheets + Epoxy (Layered structures)

$V_f = 20 \sim 35\%$

- Low ER* (In-plane direction)
- Low permeability / High rigidity
- High ER* (Through thickness direction)

CNT

Proposal

[1] Yost, Allison L., et al. *Microsystems & Nanoengineering* 1.1 (2015): 1-7.

*ER - Electrical resistance

1. Horizontally Aligned CNT Nanocomposite BP

40 times thinner
compared to
conventional BP

**High Energy
Density**

Low ER
CNT connected from bottom
to top

**High Energy
Efficiency**

**High CNT volume
fraction (~50%)**

**Low
Permeability**

**Attachable to the
Current collector**

**Reduced
Contact
Resistance**

Horizontally Aligned CNT
Nanocomposite Bipolar Plate
(HACN-BP)

Current collector (CC)

2. Experimental Procedures

2. Fabrication Process

#1: VaCNT Growth

#2: Knocking down

#3: Impregnation

#4: Attach & Co-cure

Materials coated on the Wafer

- Al₂O₃ – Buffer Layer
- Fe – Catalysts

Preparation (Gas)

- Ethylene – Carbon Source
- Hydrogen – Activated Catalysts
- Helium – Carrier gas (Inert)

2" Furnace

GNPT

- GNPT (PC-6, Precision coating, USA)

Horizontally Aligned CNT (HACNT)

- Knocked down by roller

Spin Coater (G3P-8, SCS, USA)

- Ramp (10s)
- Spin 2500 rpm (20s)

Impregnation

- Epoxy (Epon 862, Hexion, USA)
- Hardener (EPIKURE w, Hexion, USA)
- Solvent casting (Acetone)

Hot Press

- Carver (4120, Carver, USA)

Experimental condition

- 50 MPa
- Cure - 177°C, 1 hours
- Post cure - 177°C, 1 hours

2. Fabrication Process

- **Parametric study (# of specimens per group – 3)**
 - Pressure: 15, 30, 45, 60 MPa
 - Dilution concentration: 10%, 15%, 20%, 25% per pressure

2. Experimental Results – Thickness measurements

Thickness sensor

- **Measurement system**

- Laser sensor (CL-L070, Keyence, USA)

- **Parametric study**

- **Applied Pressure (MPa):** 15, 30, 45, 60
- **Dilution concentration (%):** 10, 15, 20, 25

HACN-BP's Thickness (μm)

2. Experimental Results – CNT Volume Fraction

CNT Volume fraction

$$\text{CNT volume fraction} = \frac{\text{Initial CNT array height}}{\text{Final laminate height}} (\%) * 2 \text{ (plies)}$$

Parametric study

- Applied Pressure (MPa): 15, 30, 45, 60
- Dilution concentration (%): 10, 15, 20, 25

CNT volume fraction (%)

2. Experimental Results – ER* (In-plane dir.)

4-point probe method [1]

Resistivity in in-plane direction (Ω·m)

$$\rho(\text{resistivity}) = \frac{\pi}{\ln(2)} \times \frac{\Delta V}{I} \times \text{Thickness}$$

Correction factor

$$\sigma(\text{conductivity}) = \frac{1}{\rho}$$

- Conventional BP (In-Plane): $3 \cdot 10^{-3}$
- HACN-BP, BNL (In-Plane): $5 \cdot 10^{-5} \sim 3 \cdot 10^{-4}$
- ✓ Resistivity of HACN-BP 40 times lower.

2. Experimental Results – ER* (In-plane dir.)

Sheet Resistance (Ω/sq)

$$\text{Sheet resistance } \left(\frac{\Omega}{\text{sq}} \right) = \frac{\rho(\text{resistivity})}{\text{thickness}}$$

- Sheet resistance (Ω/sq)
 - BNL (In-Plane): 3.1 (10%, 60MPa)
 - Conventional BP (In-Plane): 4.7

- The thickness was reduced by 40 times, but the sheet resistance is still lower.
 - Energy density ↑ / Resistivity ↓

2. Experimental results – Permeability

Gas permeability (μm^2)

POROLUX_1000

Permeability (μm^2)

- Permeability (μm^2)
 - HACN-BP (20 μm): 3.1 (10%, 60MPa)
 - Conventional BP (700 μm): 4.7

- Permeability is **38 times lower** in HACN-BP due to a high CNT volume fraction.

Knocked-down CNT (without polymer) → $8.7 \cdot 10^{-4} \mu\text{m}^2$
 Knocked-down CNT (with polymer) → $6.4 \cdot 10^{-7} \mu\text{m}^2$

2. Experimental Results – ER* (Through thickness dir.)

Areal Specific Resistance (ASR)

- The VRFB is composed of various parts that are compressed by high pressure, which minimizes contact resistance.
 - VRFB requires consideration of ASR measurements.

2. Experimental Results – ER* (Through thickness dir.)

① Conventional structures
(BP and CC)

② Integrated structures
(HACN-BP + CC)

❖ Cross-section

Areal specific resistance ($m\Omega\text{ cm}^2$)

- ER was lowered in ③ by eliminating contact resistance.
- As shown in ③, CNT aligned bottom to top lowers ER.

(Thickness = 1.1 cm)

(Thickness = 1 cm)

3. Conclusion

- ✓ We propose that **Horizontally Aligned CNT nanocomposite Bipolar plate (HACN-BP)** reduces the **electrical resistance by high CNT volume fraction and CNT well-aligned from bottom to top.**
- ✓ **HACN-BP also increases energy density** due to being 40 times thinner yet showing **lower permeability** than conventional BP.
- ✓ The ability to attach HACN-BP to the current collector **reduces contact resistance.** This process is **versatile** and can be applied to the BP in various sizes of PEMFC or VRFB.

THANK YOU FOR YOUR ATTENTION!

MORE INFORMATION

[1] Kaiser, Ashley L., et al. "High-volume-fraction textured carbon nanotube–bis (maleimide) and– epoxy matrix polymer nanocomposites: Implications for high-performance structural composites." *ACS Applied Nano Materials* 5.7 (2022): 9008-9023.

[2] Jeong, Kwang Il, Seung A. Song, and Seong Su Kim. "Glucose-based carbon-coating layer on carbon felt electrodes of vanadium redox flow batteries." *Composites Part B: Engineering* 175 (2019): 107072.

[3] Qian, Hui, et al. "Activation of structural carbon fibres for potential applications in multifunctional structural supercapacitors." *Journal of colloid and interface science* 395 (2013): 241-248.

